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Workload and Job Performance of Guidance and Counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between Workload and Job Performance of Guidance and Counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Two objectives and two research questions were raised to guide the study while two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised 38 lecturers. The entire population was used for the study since the population was manageable. Data for the study was gathered using self-designed questionnaires titled: "Workload of Lecturers' Questionnaire (WLLQ)" and "Job Performance Questionnaire (JPQ)". The reliability of the instrument was established with test retest method for the two instruments and the computation yielded reliability coefficients of 0.60 and 0.81. The collected data was used for analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions while t-ratio transformation associated with the correlation coefficients for each research question was used to test the corresponding hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that research project supervision and teaching of many courses as correlates of lecturers' workload positively relates with lecturers' job performance. It was recommended that The school administrators should reduce the number of students that lecturers supervise so that their job performance on other areas can be enhanced. The school administrators should reduce the number of courses that lecturers teach so that their job performance on other areas can be enhanced.

Keywords: Workload, lecturers' workload, Job performance.

INTRODUCTION

Workload is the quantity of task or assignment delegated to an employee of an organization for the employee to carry out over a specific period of time. Lecturers' workload has to do with those official and unofficial responsibilities or tasks given to Lecturers' to discharge within the university community (Amini-Philips & Okonmah, 2020). Different factors can contribute to the increase in the workload of a lecturer in this modern day dispensation. These factors could either be intrinsic (internal) or extrinsic (external). The external factors that contribute to the workload imbalance of the lecturer are those emanating from the system and which are beyond the control of the lecturer. On the other hand, the intrinsic factors are those caused by the lecturers themselves and they can be only contained by the lecturer who have the will power. Some of the external factors includes: large class size, membership of

multiple committees at the department, faculty and university levels, multiple courses being taught, multiple number of supervisees, paucity of manpower, duplication or multiplicity of courses, among others. The internal factors include: procrastination, low level of self-motivation, poor self-development, and inadequate physical capacity, among others.

Workload could be defined as the total amount of work that has to be done by a particular person or organization (Mbunda in Amini-Philips & Okonmah, 2020). Workload encompasses those duties and tasks assigned to an employee as part of his or her overall corporate responsibilities within a given business organization. Workload could also be defined as those sets of statutory responsibilities assigned to a worker in which he or she must discharge within a given period of time (Amie-Ogan & Fekarurhobo, 2020). Workload is generally divided into three parts: quantitative workload or overload, qualitative workload and under-load. The quantitative workload has to do with the act of having more tasks to perform than can be easily accomplished. The qualitative workload is those ones that can be described as being too difficult, tough or hard to deliver. The under-load is the type that makes it difficult for workers to use their skills and abilities (Gansler & Rosen, 2023).

Guidance and counselling Lecturers' workload in the view of Adeolu and Arinze (2018) are measured by the class size, subject areas, condition of service, school policy, teaching staff strength and lecturers' abilities among others. Guidance and counselling Lecturers' workload includes those academic and administrative duties carried out by lecturers in the course of performing their jobs in tertiary institutions and most especially universities (Amie-Ogan & Fekarurhobo, 2021). Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021) on their own part asserted that the act of teaching many courses, supervision of large number of undergraduates and post-graduate students and administrative duties constitute some of the workload that can influence the job performance of lecturers at the tertiary education level. These indices as identified by Adeolu and Arinze (2018) and Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021) constituted the basis of this research which as indices of lecturer's workload is aimed at determining the extent to which they promote the job performance of lecturers in Rivers State Universities.

Guidance and counselling Lecturers are the major stakeholders in the tertiary institutions whose core responsibilities are usually to teach, counsel and bring students who intend to acquire skills and gain knowledge for their personal growth and development. Following this explication, Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021) on their own part, asserted that the act of teaching many courses, supervision of large number of undergraduates and post-graduate students and administrative duties constitutes some of the workloads that can influence the job performance of Guidance and counselling lecturers. Workload of a lecturers is said not to be balanced when it generally exceeds the capacity and statutory job description of the lecturer thereby, bringing about retardation in the quality of lecturers' job performance.

In order to relatively balance Lecturers' workload, the BCF Career (2021) and Ania (2021) suggested as follows: learn to prioritize your activities and responsibilities, prepare an inventory of the day's activities, equitable delegation of responsibilities as often as possible to reduce the burden on one staff, observe break intermittently especially when it is called-for, socialize with friends and family to dampen the stress, learn to focus more on the positive aspect of your task, set-up a resource calendar and use a dedicated resource management software. Gethppy (2021) also added that maintaining a balanced workload Lecturers need to: set realistic expectations, distribute and tackle the difficult tasks first at the initial working period, increase their level of job flexibility and use planning software to engage in electronic planning. Gain (2020) also stated that, for there to be workload balance among Lecturers, task should be allocated fairly and effectively, prioritization of the tasks to be carried out by each Lecturer should be considered, allocate tasks based lecturer's skills set, delegate responsibilities based on the physical and mental abilities of the lecturer, consider the availability of the Lecturer and consider the interest of the Lecturer in the performance of the task.

In every tertiary institution of learning, lecturer's job performance is incredibly essential for the growth and development of the institution (Osman, Shariff & Lajin, 2020). Lecturers' job performance in this context is measured by the lecturers' ability to efficiently utilize the available scarce resources (time, material and human) at his or her disposal to achieve maximum productivity. Job performance of a lecturer is seen in the lecturer's ability to deliver instruction to the students using the most desirable

instructional methods and resources which will also bring about positive learning outcome in the students. In some climes, a lecturer is said to be performing better only when such performance reflects also in the academic life of the students who are the lecturers' target audience (Imran, Fatima, Zaheer, Yousaf & Batool, 2022).

According to Brown and Krager (2025), the project supervisor also needs to be sensitive to students' time and competence limitations, and to assist them to become aware of their own limitations and any constraints on them. The supervisor performs a variety of tasks, many only remotely related to monitoring and improving performance (Ali, 2020). Supervisors are expected to be mainly experts in teaching (Brown & Krager, 2025). Many tasks of supervisors are related broadly to advice. Advice is given on direction, completeness, clarity, methodology, topic selection and feedback is given on progress of written work.

Students at various levels of tertiary education programme (undergraduate and postgraduate) are expected to carry out research projects as a compulsory prerequisite for the award of degree (Gallego, Georgentzis, Montaner & Amaral, 2022). Students undergoing programmes at undergraduate and post-graduate levels are assigned to supervisors who are lecturers in the universities. These supervisors are expected to guide the students as they carry out their research work from start to finish. Many lecturers affirm that supervision is one of the most challenging and fulfilling parts of their job in the university. Supervision can play a vital role in enabling students to fulfil their potential. Helping a student to become an independent researcher is a significant achievement and can enhance the lecturer's teaching and research. Supervision is also a critical element in achieving universities' strategic aim of integrating research and education.

Supervision is widely recognized as being complex and multidimensional. Ballard and Clanchy (2023) describe research student supervision as a blend of academic expertise and the skilled management of personal and professional relations.

Similarly, Haksever and Manisali (2020) have also mentioned that the job performances of lecturers who supervise students with a balanced workload (moderate number of supervisees) are more commendable. Therefore, the workload of the lecturer in the education system is critical to a successful process and enhanced performance in the discharge of their corporate onus within the system. If poor supervision takes place as a result of increased number of students that are being supervised by a lecturer within a given period, it will bring about a significant negative impact on the students which does not only bring about a limitation on their quality of work, but also their motivation. Where the workload of the lecturer is normal or balanced especially in the area of supervision, the lecturer will also have the desire to constantly support and reassurance to the student (supervisee) of a better outcome (Haksever & Manisali, 2020; Moses, 2020) and also keep the student's morale high (Phillips & Pugh, 2020).

Cryer and Salmon (2020) maintained that there is the need for the number of students being supervised by a supervisor to reduce bearably so that they can consider improving their performance by supporting their supervisees (students) via pastoral care and advice provision, sympathy and encouragement. Workload influences the job performance of lecturers as it makes it difficult for lecturers to thoroughly read the student's written work so as to provide constructive criticism, since this is an essential element in the student's intellectual development (Spear, 2020). In addition to this, is the major assumption that due to the increased number of supervisees, observations have shown that some supervisors tend to be unduly slow in reading thesis drafts and other written materials.

Welch (2020) suggests three styles of supervision. Firstly, she described the highly directive approach, which is very structured with the student being given a lot of advice in the early stages. This level of control diminished as the student gained a confidence and ability. The second approach is highly directive at the beginning and the end of the project with a highly non-directive period in the middle. Finally, the third approach was described as highly directive with close monitoring of the student throughout the project. Rajah-Kanagasabai and Roberts (2025) describe project student supervision as a blend of academic expertise and the skilled management of personal and professional relations. Some writers, such as Roberts and Seaman (2018) discuss the patterns and process of supervision and especially the roles of postgraduate students in producing effective supervision. supervisor ensure that the student does the study

properly, as well also to teach the student about general research practices, scientific rigour, independence, and critical thinking. Effective project supervision of research students is acknowledged to be a crucial factor in the latter's successful completion of the programme.

How well they are supervised is likely to be linked to the way they choose to occupy their role. This kind of experience is very interesting and meaningful to appropriate persons like students, supervisors and schools in order that they may examine what they should do and how they should go about playing their roles optimally. Project supervision is a capstone experiences that provide students with an opportunity to answer a research question within a disciplinary framework under supervision (Ashwin, Abbas & McLean, 2019).

Course allocation is one aspect of the teaching process. Course allocation involves the scheduling of a certain number of academic staff to teach course(s) over a definite period of time. The scheduling, which takes into consideration the contact hours per week (credit load) and the teaching load per week for each staff, is formulated in this study as an integer programming problem with the objective of allocating courses to the staff according to their preferences without violating certain functional constraints due to the contact hours per week and the teaching load. The problem considered here deals with the allocation of courses on a semester basis for an undergraduate programme in a department. A department may be composed of lecturers who specialise in different subject areas. Even so, the number of specialized lecturers in an area may exceed the number of undergraduate courses available for the semester in that area. Conversely, the number of specialised lecturers in a subject area may be too few when compared to the number of courses. This is a problem to most HODs. Should the HOD assign lecturers according to their subject area, some lecturers may exceed their teaching load, while others would be underutilised. Further to this problem is that there are constraints on the contact hours per week and the teaching load per week for each lecturer.

Angela, Damian and Graham (2018) proposed a system whereby courses can be allocated to lecturers based on their preferred courses with respect to their areas of specialization. This is a bold step towards efficient course allocation. However, the system did not go further to assess the performance of a lecturer on the course(s) assigned to him/her to justify his/her continuous teaching of the course(s), or whether there is a need for some readjustments. This is why Richard and Rebeca (2019), is of the opinion that inasmuch as students are being assessed by lecturers (through tests, quizzes, assignments, practical and exams) to ascertain their academic performances, lecturers should equally be assessed by students to ascertain their teaching performances in class. Angela (2018) suggested the use of the following yardstick for assessing a lecturer: level of understanding of the course, ability to relate the subject to other disciplines or to practical use, attitude of the lecturer to students such as, punctuality in class, being audible in class, writing legibly in class, ability to ask and answer questions and being enthusiastic/humorous in class.

Richard (2022) noted that lecturers in most institutions in Nigeria are made to teach up to five, six or more courses per week in the various programmes offered in the school (pre-degree, regular, part time, post-graduate and sandwich). Consequently, most lecturers in universities in Nigeria have reported stress levels high enough to interfere with their health, sleep and the quality of their work. According to Martin (2022), the process of lecturing includes teaching, examining students' performance, laboratory supervision of experiments carried out by students, and supervision of student's research. Given all the activities involved in lecturing, one would expect that lecturers would be saddled with few courses to ensure efficiency in teaching. However, this is not the case as lecturers take several courses in programmes at a given time in the university. Participating in continuing education courses is also included when these are organized as part of the activities of the schools. Teaching is a set of events, outside the learners which are designed to support internal process of learning. Teaching (Instruction) is outside the learner. Learning is internal to learners. You cannot motivate others if you are not self-motivated. Motives are not seen, but, behaviors are seen. Is learning a motive or behavior? Learning is both a motive and behavior but only behavior is seen, learning is internal, performance is external.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of job performance of these lecturers also depends on the way in which their workload is normalized. In an ideal situation, lecturers are supposed to work in an environment where tasks are prioritized, and task fairly allocated to lecturers according to their skills and abilities so as to bring about the normalization of their workload. Regrettably, this appears not to be the case in Rivers State Universities today as some lectures are overloaded with much work that becomes detrimental to the academic growth of the institution as a whole. Some of the lecturers are involved in multiple committees within the university community, effective assessment of many students, teaching large classes, attendance of conferences, research and publication, research project supervision of many students and teaching of many courses and also carry out other administrative functions in some instances. This in turn has the capacity to affect their job performance. It is on this ground that this study seeks to ascertain the relationship between Workload and Job Performance of Guidance and Counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State

Purpose of the Study

The aim of the study is to determine relationship between Workload and Job Performance of Guidance and Counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between research project supervision of many students and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between research project supervision of students and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State
2. There is no significant relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

METHODS

The study investigated relationship between Workload and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A correlation research design was adopted for the study. A total of 38 lecturers formed the population of the study. The entire population was used for the study since the population was manageable. Data for the study was gathered using self-designed questionnaires titled: "Workload of Business Education lecturers' Questionnaire (WLBELQ)" and "Job Performance Questionnaire (JPQ)". The questionnaires were validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established with test retest method for the two instruments and the computation yielded reliability coefficients of 0.60 and 0.81. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to analyze the research questions while t-transformation was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.?*

Table 1: Computed Result Showing the Relationship between Research Project Supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Level of Relationship
Research Project Supervision students (x)	16.7	60.3	54.6	0.80	Strong positive relationship
Job performance(y)	20.9	63.2			

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The computed r-value of 0.80 shows the relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The calculated coefficient indicates positive interaction of the existing relationship and the result however shows very strong positive relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question 2. *There is no significant relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Computed Result Showing the Relationship between Teaching of Many Courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Level of Relationship
Teaching many courses (x)	16.4	54.1	45.8	0.71	Strong positive relationship
Job performance(y)	20.9	63.2			

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The computed r-value of 0.71 shows the relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The calculated coefficient indicates positive interaction of the existing relationship and the result however shows a strong positive relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant relationship between research project supervision of students and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.*

Table 3: Analysis of Computed Correlation showing Relationship between Research Project Supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	t-trans	t-crit	Df	Level of sign	Decision
Research Project of supervision of students (x)	16.9	63.3	51.5	21.5	1.96	98	0.05	Significant
Job Performance (Y)	20.9	63.2						

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The result of the hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance showed the t-value of 21.5 is higher than t-critical of 1.96. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4: Analysis of Computed Correlation showing Relationship between Teaching of Many Courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

Variables	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	t-trans	t-crit	Df	Level of sign	Decision
	Σy	Σy^2						
Teaching of Many Courses (x)	16.4	54.1					0.05	
Job Performance (Y)	20.9	63.3	42.3	20.1	1.96	98		Significant

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The result of the hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance showed the t-value of 20.1 is higher than t-critical of 1.960. Thus, the hypothesis implies a significant relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship Between Research Project Supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

The computed r-value of 0.80 shows the relationship between research project supervision and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The calculated t-transformation of 21.5 coefficient indicates positive relationship and the result however shows high level of relationship research project supervision and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The result of the tested hypothesis also indicates that there is a significant relationship between research and publication and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. This agrees with the work of Brown and Krager (2020) where it was reported that the project supervisor also needs to be sensitive to students' time and competence limitations, and to assist them to become aware of their own limitations and any constraints on them. It also agrees with the work of Ali (2020) who stated that the supervisor performs a variety of tasks, many only remotely related to monitoring and improving performance.

Relationship Between Teaching of Many Courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

The computed r-value of 0.71 shows the relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The calculated t-transformation of 20.1 coefficient indicates positive relationship and the result however shows low level of relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The result of the tested hypothesis also indicates that there is a significant relationship between teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. This agrees with the work of Angela, Damian and Graham (2018) who proposed a system whereby courses can be allocated to lecturers based on their preferred courses with respect to their areas of specialization. This is a bold step towards efficient course allocation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings in the study, it was concluded that there is a relationship between research project supervision, teaching of many courses and Job Performance of Guidance and counselling Lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. The school administrators should reduce the number of students that lecturers supervise so that their job performance on other areas can be enhanced.
2. The school administrators should reduce the number of courses that lecturers teach so that their job performance on other areas can be enhanced.

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